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Notes on the name *Lethrotrypes* Jacobson, 1892 and taxonomic status of *Parathorectes pueblai* López-Colón et Bahillo De la Puebla, 2022 (Coleoptera: Geotrupidae)

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Abstract. History of usage of the name *Lethrotrypes* Jacobson, 1892 is discussed. New synonyms are established: *Lethrotrypes* Jacobson, 1892 = *Parathorectes* López-Colón et Bahillo De la Puebla, 2022, **syn. n.**, *Trypocopris* (*Lethrotrypes*) *inermis* (Ménétriés, 1832) = *Parathorectes pueblai* López-Colón et Bahillo De la Puebla, 2022, **syn. n.**

Key words: Coleoptera, Geotrupidae, *Trypocopris* (*Lethrotrypes*) *inermis*, *Parathorectes pueblai*, synonymy, Western Caucasus.

Замечания о названии *Lethrotrypes* Jacobson, 1892 и таксономическом статусе *Parathorectes pueblai* López-Colón et Bahillo De la Puebla, 2022 (Coleoptera: Geotrupidae)

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Резюме. Рассмотрена история использования названия *Lethrotrypes* Jacobson, 1892. Установлена новая синонимия: *Lethrotrypes* Jacobson, 1892 = *Parathorectes* López-Colón et Bahillo De la Puebla, 2022, **syn. n.**, *Trypocopris* (*Lethrotrypes*) *inermis* (Ménétriés, 1832) = *Parathorectes pueblai* López-Colón et Bahillo De la Puebla, 2022, **syn. n.**

Ключевые слова: Coleoptera, Geotrupidae, *Trypocopris* (*Lethrotrypes*) *inermis*, *Parathorectes pueblai*, синонимия, Западный Кавказ.

Taxon *Lethrotrypes* Jacobson, 1892 was established by Jacobson [1892] as a subgenus in the genus *Thorectes* Mulsant, 1842 for two species: Caucasian *Geotrupes inermis* Ménétriés, 1832 and *G. fausti* Reitter, 1890 from North Iran and Talysch without type species designation. Reitter [1893] transferred both species to the subgenus *Trypocopris* Motschulsky, 1860 of the genus *Geotrupes* Latreille, 1797, placing *G. inermis* to the separate group *Lethrotrypes* without definite taxonomic status and considering *G. fausti* together with the rest species of the subgenus.

Boucomont [1902] re-included *Lethrotrypes* (mentioned as *Lethrotrypes* (*sic*)) in the genus *Thorectes* as a subgenus, and later [Boucomont, 1912] considered *Lethrotrypes* as a synonym of the subgenus *Thorectes* in the genus *Geotrupes*.

Subsequently, *G. inermis* was also included in the subgenus *Trypocopris* of the genus *Geotrupes* without mentioning the name proposed by Jacobson [Olsoufieff, 1918; Medvedev, 1965]. In the review establishing the modern generic structure of Geotrupinae [Zunino, 1984], *Lethrotrypes* was omitted. Later Baraud [1992], following Boucomont [1902] considered *Lethrotrypes* (also mentioned as *Lethrotrypes* (*sic*)) as a subgenus in the genus *Thorectes* and formally designated *G. inermis* as a type species.

López-Colón [1994] proposed the combination *Trypocopris* (*Lethrotrypes*) *inermis* (Ménétriés, 1832) for the first time. However, this work in its full form turned out to be inaccessible to most researchers, with the exception of the annotation, which mistakenly indicated that the author had placed the species to a monotypic genus. Probably because of that, Palmer, Cambefort [1997] also mentioned *Lethrotrypes* as a monotypic genus, and Nikolajev [2006] re-established the same combination, *Trypocopris* (*Lethrotrypes*) *inermis* as comb. nov., which was criticized by López-Colón [2006].

The species *T. (L.) inermis* undoubtedly belongs to *Trypocopris* by the structure of male genitalia, but the shape of the antennal club and the winglessness makes it similar externally to *Thorectes* species. The range of this species is limited to the Western Caucasus (Russia: Krasnodar Region, Karachay-Cherkessia; Abkhazia).

López-Colón et Bahillo De la Puebla [2022] described *Parathorectes pueblai* López-Colón et Bahillo De la Puebla, 2022 from a single specimen from Karachay-Cherkessia (Russia). In their work, the new taxon was compared only with the genera close to *Thorectes*, but at the same time, *Trypocopris* (*Lethrotrypes*) *inermis* was not mentioned.

Described in detail and well-illustrated characters of *P. pueblai* fully correspond to those of *T. (L.) inermis*,

which allows us to establish the following new synonymy: *Lethrotrypes* Jacobson, 1892 = *Parathorectes* López-Colón et Bahillo De la Puebla, 2022, **syn. n.**, *Trypocopris* (*Lethrotrypes*) *inermis* (Ménétriés, 1832) = *Parathorectes pueblai* López-Colón et Bahillo De la Puebla, 2022, **syn. n.**

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